

Aggregating Telematics for Road Safety Analysis

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Introduction

- Road safety is a significant **global concern** which have implications on economic, public health, and development areas.
- **IVORY** is a Horizon Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Industrial Doctoral Network, aiming to develop **AI solutions** to enhance road safety.
- DC9 research focuses on **spatial analysis** providing insights into risk zones.
- It incorporates **telematics data** capturing real-time driving behavior.
- **Telematics integration** in road networks enables targeted safety interventions.

Data Overview

- GDPR-compliant **telematics data** from OSeven, collected at **1Hz** via smartphone sensors, fully anonymized, and spanning multiple trips from numerous drivers over the last **four months of 2024**.
- ❖ **SpeedingFlag, Mobile_usage, Harsh_acc** and **Harsh_brk**
Binary indicators (event occurred or not) → Aggregation by summing per spatial entity.
- ❖ **Event_intensity**
Ordinal scale (1 to 3), indicating severity of harsh events → Aggregation by averaging, excluding cases where both harsh events are 0.
- ❖ **Trips_count** and **Points_count**
Total number of trips recorded, and data points collected → Aggregation by counting per spatial entity.
- ❖ **SmoothedSpeed**
Continuous variable (vehicle speed at each point) → Aggregation by averaging per spatial entity, excluding cases where speed is 0.
- **OpenStreetMap (OSM) data** used to extract the road network, providing the spatial framework onto which telematics data were mapped.

Mapping Telematics to Road Network

- Telematics points were linked to their **nearest OSM edge** using Euclidean distance, enabling accurate **aggregation** of data per **road segment**.
- A simple buffer approach may include **additional neighboring nodes** causing incorrect association of telematics data to the origin node.
 - Telematics points inside the buffer may relate to other **nearby nodes**. Resulting in a **distorted representation** of traffic flow for the origin node.
- A simple buffer approach can create **“isolated” nodes**.
 - These nodes are characterized by telematics data, whereas the **outgoing edges** lack such data.
 - It occurs when a buffer covers **several edges**, but the edges directly connected to the origin node lack telematics data.

Node-Level Aggregation: A New Approach

- Refined buffer method adds a **key constraint**:
 - Telematics points must be **within the buffer** and **located on edges connected to the origin node**.
- **Final assumptions**:
 - Drivers influence the characteristics of nodes within a **buffer radius**.
 - Drivers influencing the node are those traveling **along the edges** intersecting at that node, and thus directly affecting its **traffic flow**. Consequently, influencing telematics points must be located on these **edges**.
 - A point p is **considered on edge** e only if e is the nearest edge to p .
- A first **comparison** of the two approaches was performed using a **50-meter buffer** around the origin node.
 - The features were **aggregated** as presented before.
 - The simple buffer approach yields a dataset of 34886 nodes (**DF1**).
 - By using the novel approach, a second dataset of 31924 nodes is generated (**DF2**).

Comparison through Learning-based Models

- 1) Standard Deviation (**SD**).
 - A **lower SD** means data points more concentrated around the mean indicating **greater homogeneity**.
 - A **higher SD** indicates a **more heterogeneous dataset**.
- 2) Principal Component Analysis (**PCA**) transforms features into principal components that capture **maximum variance**. The Proportion of Variance Explained (**PVE**) reveals the dataset's structure:
 - A dominant first component suggests a simple and **concentrated structure**.
 - An evenly distributed PVEs indicate a more **complex dataset**.
- 3) Autoencoder (**AE**) learns a latent representation of input data, capturing **non-linear relationships**:
 - Encoder-Decoder: $Z = f_{\theta}(X)$, $\hat{X} = g_{\phi}(Z)$
 - A low reconstruction error implies that the latent representation captures the **essential features** of the data.
 - A higher reconstruction error suggests that no compact latent space can fully capture the **data's variability**.

Results (1/2)

➤ Standard Deviation Reduction:

- Our approach **reduced data dispersion** across features.

Feature	Standard Deviation in DF1 (34886 nodes)	Standard Deviation in DF2 (31924 nodes)
smoothenedSpeed	11.76	10.26
SpeedingFlag	59.14	30.90
Mobile_usage	50.07	26.64
Harsh_acc	3.68	1.96
Harsh_brk	2.09	1.32
Event_intensity	0.81	0.75
Trips_count	108.79	54.80
Points_count	1291.68	657.37

➤ PCA Results:

- PCA showed more **evenly distributed** explained variance in **DF2**, indicating higher **homogeneity**.
- **DF1's first principal component** explains nearly half the variance, while **DF2's variance** is spread more evenly.

PCA Explained Variance Comparison (Top 6 Components)

Results (2/2)

Autoencoder training:

- Same architecture and hyperparameters used on DF1 and DF2 to extract features, comparing **reconstruction errors** and **loss curves** to evaluate how well each **latent space** represents the data.
- **Encoding layer sizes** tested: 2, 4, 6.
- **Training:** Adam optimizer (lr=0.005), batch size=64, epochs=200, early stopping=5.

Key Findings

- AE reconstructs DF1 better than DF2, indicating **simpler patterns** and easier reconstruction in DF1.
- DF2 likely captures **more complex**, realistic variability, making reconstruction **more challenging**.
- DF1 shows **higher variance** but simpler relationships; DF2 is **more diverse** and less redundant.

Discussion

- The present work analyzes methods for **integrating telematics data** into a **map**.
 - Nearest-road aggregation is **straightforward** and it is believed to ensure a reliable representation of the data as it builds on their **proximity** and **contextual relevance**.
 - A **simple buffer-based approach** to node aggregation may be too simplistic.
- The **presented node aggregation** approach extends the simple buffer method by introducing an additional constraint for **improved representation**.
 - The resulting dataset exhibits **reduced variability** and **lower overdispersion** compared to the simpler buffer-based approach and it is **more challenging to reconstruct** using DL tools.
 - These observations, alongside the presented assumptions, support the interpretation that the dataset DF2 more accurately reflects **real-world driving behavior** and **spatial dynamics** resulting in a more realistic dataset with more complex and fragmented patterns.
- Analyses leveraging **telematics-informed road networks** can be enhanced.

Conclusions

- **Combining data** with spatial entities represents a **crucial step** in spatial analysis enabling the contextualization of dynamic driving behavior within the network.
- The present work moves beyond simplistic methods by utilizing a **more structured framework** that better represents traffic flow within the real-world environment.
- Statistical and machine learning tools can be used to compare the **data complexity** of the datasets derived from different aggregation methods.
 - By making additional assumptions, the new approach generates a dataset with **lower variance** and **more complex structure**, confirming that it more faithfully represents **real-world conditions**.

Future Research

- Future work can improve upon these aggregation ideas by considering **additional perspectives** or maybe **expanding the dataset** to examine geographical and temporal variations.
- More advanced **DL techniques**, such as Variational Autoencoder, could offer a deeper understanding of the data's nature when aggregated, with more robust findings.
- Spatial models can be employed to extract meaningful **spatial insights** from the comparison.
- Lastly, the entire work is based on a **50-meter buffer**, though varying distances might offer more insights.

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